

Exploring Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder with Positive Psychological Constructs: A Relational Analysis

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The study investigated the relationship between Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD) severity and four positive psychological constructs: Values, Self-Compassion, Psychological Flexibility, and Equanimity. Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is a mental health condition characterised by primarily the symptoms of obsessions and compulsions. Positive psychological constructs, viz., Values, Self-Compassion, Psychological Flexibility and Equanimity in patients with OCD and its relation with the disorder helps viewing the disorder from a comprehensive lens. A sample of 39 patients diagnosed with OCD was assessed using the Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) (Goodman et al., 1989), Neff's Self-Compassion Scale (Neff, 2003), the Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (AAQ-II), the Equanimity Questionnaire (Bond et al., 2011), and the Valued Living Questionnaire (VLQ) (Wilson & Groom, 2002). Pearson Correlation and Linear Regression analyses revealed that OCD severity significantly predicts lower levels of self-compassion ($R^2 = .173$) and valued living ($R^2 = .158$), while strongly predicting increased psychological inflexibility ($R^2 = .351$). No significant relationship was found with equanimity. These findings suggest that OCD symptoms deeply impact the psychological mechanisms of flexibility and self-kindness, highlighting the need for third wave interventions in clinical practice.

Keywords: OCD, psychological flexibility, self-compassion, valued living, equanimity

Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is a mental disorder which is characterised by the presence of obsessions and compulsions in patients. Obsessions are persistent, intrusive, and distressing ideas, thoughts, or urges and impulses. Compulsions are recurrent and repetitive ritualistic behavioural or mental acts that individuals feel compelled to do as to avoid or lessen suffering, anxiety, distress or to forestall some feared event or condition (Stein et al., 2016). Uncontrollably intrusive thoughts, mental images, urges or impulses that are persistent and recurrent are the clinical characteristics of an obsession. While wanting to escape these thoughts, the person is unable to do so. The thoughts are unpleasant, intrusive, and illogical in character. These thoughts are accompanied by uncomfortable emotions like fear, uncertainty, guilt, shame, etc. (Stein et al., 2016). Compulsion is characterised by the recurrence of certain behaviour or beliefs that a person exhibits to balance off, combat, or relieve themselves from their obsessions. In the absence of a more effective

copied mechanism, people with OCD tend to rely on the compulsion as a means of brief relief from their obsessions, even though they understand the relief the compulsion brings is temporary (Stein et al., 2016).

According to Hayes et al. (1999), values can be understood and defined as "freely chosen, verbally constructed consequences of ongoing, dynamic, evolving patterns of activity, which establish dominant reinforcers for that activity that are intrinsic in engagement in the valued behavioural pattern itself. Value explains the degree of significance of something or an activity to choose the best course of action, the best way to live for the person, unique to them, or to explain the motivation behind various behaviours and life choices (Rokeach, 1973). Human behaviour is guided by values. Values serve as the foundation for identifying the level of awareness that influences and motivates (Schwartz, 1992). Michelson et al. (2011) in a study found that restricted valued action contributed variance to reduced quality of life over and above the contributions of gender, symptom severity, experiential avoidance, distress about emotions, and depression comorbidity in patients.

Wetterneck et al. (2013) revealed significant relationships between OCD severity and self-compassion, courage and valued living. Instead of invalidating our suffering or criticizing ourselves excessive with self-criticism, self-compassion translates to being kind and sympathetic towards ourselves when we fail, suffer, or feel inadequate (Neff, 2003). Compassion, in literal terms translates to "suffering with." When someone affirms to have compassion for another being, it is assumed that the person either voluntarily or involuntarily "suffers" with that other. Self-compassion is a safeguard for those who have a sensitive heart and are empathetic as people, preventing them from sinking into a debilitating sense of worthlessness due to their failure to help the person who is suffering or in great need. Eichholz et al. (2020) concluded that there was a negative correlation between self-compassion and disturbed

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emotion regulation. Emotional regulation predicted symptom severity when controlling for obsessions and depressive symptoms. Van et al. (2010) stated that self-compassion acts as a significant predictor of symptom severity and quality of life. Study further revealed that self-compassion causes more deviations in psychopathology than mindfulness. It also revealed that self-compassion reflects complex nature of relationship between mindful constructs and health.

According to Kashdan and Rotterburg (2010), psychological flexibility is "the measurement of how a person adapts to fluctuating situational demands, re-configures mental resources, shifts perspective, and balances competing desires, needs, and life domains." Psychological flexibility, according to Hayes et al. (2004), is "contacting the present moment as a conscious human being, and, based on what that situation affords, acting in accordance with one's chosen values" (Bond et al., 2006). Psychological flexibility is described as "the process of contacting the present moment as a conscious human being and persisting in or changing behaviour in the service of chosen values" (Hayes et al., 2006) in the ACT model. In layman's words, psychological flexibility is essentially awareness of the present moment and behavioural change that moves towards behaviours based on ideals. Thompson et al. (2021) found in their study that greater self-as-content was associated with more severe mental distress and the presence of unwanted and unacceptable thoughts.

Equanimity referred to as "neutral feeling," is a mental experience that is neither pleasant nor unpleasant and neither intensifies nor detracts from the present state of mind (Bodhi, 2000). Scriptures, religious doctrines, and philosophical systems all regard equanimity as a mental condition and essential lesson. However, psychology has only just begun to pay attention to it. It can be described as an even-minded and neutral mental state or dispositional tendencies towards all experiences or objects, independent of their affective valence (pleasant, unpleasant, or neutral), or source (Desbordes et al., 2015).

Wongpakaran et al. (2021) in their study have revealed that the effect of perceived stress and neuroticism on depression can be alleviated by increasing levels of equanimity. Dambrun and Shankland (2020) also revealed positive relationships between the components of equanimity and both formal and informal mindfulness practices in stress reduction.

There is acute paucity of research studies which have studied the relationship between the different positive psychological constructs and OCD in the Indian context. Looking at this research gap it occurred to the researcher to explore these areas and have a better understanding of dynamics at work in OCD.

Write Concluding Lines for Above Literature

Rationale

Obsessive Compulsive Disorder is a debilitating psychological disorder which often remains unreported and undiagnosed due to lack of mental health awareness, stigma, diagnostic difficulties and many other reasons. Its etiology is associated with many biopsychosocial factors and has a great impact on person's self-care as it causes impairments in social and occupational functioning. Because of its mostly continuous course there is a necessity to provide suitable interventions to prevent OCD symptoms from worsening. There is also an acute paucity of research to assess the efficacy of such interventions on certain positive psychological variables, which also may have a significant impact on reducing the severity of OCD symptoms or even preventing them to a great degree. This study focuses on the salient clinical implications in understanding how positive psychological variables are related to Obsessive Compulsive Disorder.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

- To investigate the relationship between OCD and the positive psychological constructs, viz., Values, Self- Compassion, Psychological Flexibility and Equanimity in patients.
- Hypotheses For the purpose of fulfilling the above aims, the following hypotheses had been formulated:
 - H1 There is a significant relationship between OCD and
 - H1A: Values
 - H1B: Self Compassion
 - H1C: Psychological Flexibility
 - H1D: Equanimity
 - H2 OCD predicts
 - H2A: Values
 - H2B: Self-Compassion
 - H2C: Psychological Flexibility
 - H2D: Equanimity

Method

Participants

The sample of the study comprised of 39 patients, both males and females diagnosed with obsessive compulsive disorder within the following groups. Sample was selected using the technique of purposive sampling, as per the below mentioned inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with OCD according to ICD 10 diagnostic criteria (WHO, 1992)
- Patients with mild to moderate severity of OCD
- Age between 25-45 years
- Patients stabilized on medication for 2 months
- Minimum educational qualification of 12th standard
- Ability to comprehend English language

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of any organic disorder, Epilepsy, any other neurological disorders and Intellectual disability
- Patients with history of serious medical conditions
- Patients with Dysthymia or Depression with Psychotic Features
- Patients with history of any other serious psychological disorder
- Patients diagnosed concurrently with any Personality Disorder or Alcohol or Psychoactive Substance use disorder
- Patients having undergone any psychological intervention for OCD in last year
- Patients with severe OCD
- Patients undergone ECT treatment in past or present

Research Design

Study was carried out based on mixed research design. For H1 and H2 a Causal research design was used

Measures

Case History Performa (developed for the study) This includes the detailed case history of the patient which comprises of their socio-demographic profile, chief symptoms and Complaints, History of current illness, negative history, personal history and family history, premorbid personality and temperament and mental status examination.

Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsion Scale (Goodman et al., 1989): It is a semi-structured interview which assesses symptom severity of OCD. It is measured on a 10-item symptom severity that measures symptom intensity independent of symptom subtype and a checklist of typical obsessions and compulsions. A score of 07 indicates subclinical symptoms, 815 means mild symptoms, 1623 imply moderate symptoms, 2431 severe symptoms, and 3240 extreme symptoms. The total score is between 0 to 40. Additionally, there is a subscale score (range 020) for obsessions and compulsions which can be obtained separately from the scale. Goodman et al. (1989) validated this scale by observing a significant correlation between the Y-BOCS and two separate measures of OCD. OCD symptom changes can affect Y-BOCS. Additionally, the Y-BOCS exhibits good interrater reliability and great internal consistency (Goodman et al., 1989).

Valued Living Questionnaire (Wilson & Groom, 2002): This self-statement scale is a measure of valued life. Ten life areas are included in the scale, which is used to determine whether or not individuals live their life in accordance with the values. The subscales "Importance" and "Coherence" are the two that exist in the scale. Ten items make up each subscale, and each item was assessed on a 10-point Likert scale (1 *being not important* to 10 *being extremely important*). According to the scale's scoring system, high scores are suggestive of a life that is very value-oriented. The Importance and Consistency answers for each category are multiplied, and the average of those values is then computed to determine the Valued Living composite. The Valued Living Composite scores that are obtained can vary from 10 to 100. Test-retest reliability for this tool has been credible (Cotter, 2011).

The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire II (Bond et al., 2011): This tool is a 7-item measure of psychological inflexibility. The alternatives for responses are 1 for "Never true" and 7 for "Always true." For instance, "I'm afraid of my feelings" is an AAQ-II item. Elevated overall scores on the AAQ-II correlate with increased experience avoidance, psychological rigidity, and probable psychological discomfort. Low scores indicate greater psychological adaptability. The adequate discriminant validity of the AAQ-II is demonstrated. Better psychometric consistency is seen in the AAQ-II ($r=.97$), which seems to measure the same notion as the AAQ-I (Bond et al. 2011).

Self-Compassion Scale (Neff, 2003): This scale entails 26-items with 6 subscales. The scales are self-kindness subscale that has 5 items, the 5-item self-judgment subscale, common humanity subscale constitutes of 4 items along with the 4-item isolation subscale, mindfulness subscale and over-identification subscale. It is a 5-point scale from 1= "almost never" to 5= "almost always". The scoring method comprises of calculating the Mean scores on the six subscales to create an overall self-compassion score. The scale has shown to have a good internal and test retest reliability in research,

(Neff, 2003). The internal consistency reliability obtained was $\alpha=.94$.

Equanimity Questionnaire (Shires & Cayoun, 2021): This is a 16-item self-report measure. It was developed for adults 18 years of age and above. It is a useful tool in the therapeutic context to examine the factors of experiential avoidance and a client's emotional reactivity. There are two subscales in the tool: Experiential acceptance (items 18): this refers to a mindset that accepts all internal experiences (thoughts, feelings, bodily sensations, etc.) without trying to resist or cling to them. Non-Reactivity (items 916): This scale measures a person's lack of reaction to situations that hinder them from being attached to or averse to them (e.g., ideas, emotions). According to Rogers et al. (2021), the scale possesses strong internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha=.88$), test-retest reliability over a period of two to six weeks, and both convergent and divergent validity.

Procedure

The ethical clearance for conducting this research was obtained from the ethics committee of IIS (Deemed to be) University, Jaipur. The study was conducted in two phases. The Data was collected from tertiary care mental health hospitals. Psychiatric centres and clinics in Jaipur Rajasthan. Participants were recruited for the study on regular basis. Informed consent was obtained from the participants. These patients were administered the tools of the study. This included Case History Performa (developed for the study), Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsion Scale (Goodman et al., 1989), Valued Living Questionnaire (Wilson & Groom 2002), The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (Hayes et al., 2004), Self-Compassion Scale (Neff, 2003), and Equanimity Questionnaire (Shires & Cayoun, 2021). Post assessments the data was analysed and trends were studied.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was done using IBM SPSS-25. Various descriptive statistics like Mean, SD, Frequency and Percentages and Inferential statistics like Pearson Correlation, regression, ANOVA were used and the trends were studied.

- Mean, Standard Deviation
- Correlation
- Regression

Results and Discussion

As per table 1, the sample ($N=39$) had a mean age of 26.08 years ($SD = 5.92$), indicating a relatively young adult group. Regarding gender, 61.5% were male and 38.5% female.

Occupational status was diverse with most were students (41%), followed by unemployed (33%), employed (15%), homemakers (8%), and others (3%). Marital status was predominantly single (85%), with 15% married. In terms of socioeconomic and residential backgrounds, the majority were middle-class (79%) and from urban (67%) or semi-urban (10%) areas, with only 23% residing in rural settings. The religious affiliation was mainly Hindu (92%), reflecting the regional demographic composition of the sample. Regarding family type, most belonged to nuclear families (74%).

Table 1
Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Variable	Mean (SD)	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	26.08 (5.92)			
Gender		Male	24	61.54
		Female	15	38.46
Occupation		Student	16	41.03
		Employed	6	15.38
		Unemployed	13	33.33
		Homemaker	3	7.69
		Others	1	2.56
Religion		Hindu	36	92.31
		Muslim	2	5.13
		Others	1	2.56
Marital status		Single	33	84.62
		Married	6	15.38
Residence		Rural	9	23.08
		Urban	26	66.67
		Semi-Urban	4	10.26
Socio-Economic Status		Low	1	2.56
		Middle	31	79.49
		High	7	17.95
Type of Family		Nuclear	29	74.36
		Joint	10	25.64

Note. Mean and standard deviation are reported for age. Frequencies and percentages are reported for categorical variables.

Table 2
Pearson Correlations among OCD Severity and Psychological Constructs (N = 39)

Variable	1	2	3	4	5
1. OCD	-				
2. Self-Compassion	-.416**	-			
3. Psychological Flexibility	-.514**	-.531**	-		
4. Valued Living	-.395*	-.505**	-.169	-	
5. Equanimity	-.135	-.307	-.405*	.226	-

Note. N=39, OCD=obsessive compulsive disorder, $p < .05$. $p < .01$

Table 2 shows the Pearson correlations between OCD severity and key psychological constructs. OCD severity demonstrated a significant inverse relationship with self-compassion ($r = -.416, p < .01$), indicating that higher levels of OCD symptoms were associated with lower self-compassion.

Psychological Flexibility was measured using the AAQ-II, where higher scores indicate greater psychological inflexibility. Thus, the positive correlation between OCD and Psychological Flexibility ($r = .514, p < 0.01$) indicates that increased OCD symptoms are associated with increased psychological inflexibility. The role of experiential avoidance in OCD has been extensively supported in ACT-based research. The findings are having similarity with the findings of Twohig et al. (2010) who found that experiential avoidance is a core pathological process in OCD, where the rigid attempt to suppress obsessions actually leads to an increase in intensity of the symptoms.

A significant negative correlation with valued living ($r = -.395, p < .05$) suggests that individuals with more severe OCD symptoms engage less in values-congruent living. Twohig et al. (2010) found

that compulsive behaviors often negatively impact one's alignment with personal values. Furthermore, Abramowitz et al. (2009) found that individuals who engage in higher levels of experiential avoidance are more likely to experience intense distress from intrusive thoughts

In contrast, equanimity showed a negative but non-significant correlation with OCD severity ($r = -.135, p > .05$), indicating that equanimity may not be as strongly linked with symptom severity in the current sample. It is possible that while OCD patients feel intense distress, they may still maintain a baseline level of non-reactivity in areas of life besides their specific obsessions.

Overall, these findings provide empirical support to Hypotheses 1A (valued living), 1B (self-compassion), and 1C (psychological flexibility), but not 1D (equanimity). Hence Hypothesis 1 was partially accepted.

Table 3
Simple Linear Regression Predicting Valued Living from OCD Severity (N = 39)

Predictor	B	SE	Bβ	t	p
OCD	-0.395	0.151	-0.395	-2.62	<.013
Constant	-4.200	0.600	-	-7.00	<.001

Note. $R^2 = .158, F(1, 37) = 6.85, p = .013$. OCD = obsessive-compulsive disorder

Table 3 depicts linear regression to examine whether OCD severity predicts valued living. The overall model was significant, $F(1, 37) = 6.85, p = .013$, and accounted for approximately 15.8% of the variance in valued living ($R^2 = .158$). The regression coefficient for OCD severity was $-0.395 (SE = 0.151, \beta = -0.395)$, indicating that for each point increase in OCD severity, valued living scores decreased by approximately -0.395 points ($t = -2.62, p = .013$). These results support Hypothesis 1A that greater OCD severity predicts lower engagement in valued living values. The present study's finding is strongly corroborated by Wetterneck et al. (2013). Their research implied that the functional impairment caused by obsessive-compulsive symptoms creates a significant barrier to valued action, leading to a decrease in the quality of life as symptoms intensify.

It can be understood that when the compulsions take up hours of the day, there is little energy left for meaningful life areas like family, work, or personal growth.

Table 4
Simple Linear Regression Predicting Self-Compassion from OCD Severity (N = 39)

Predictor	B	SE	Bβ	t	p
OCD	-0.416	0.149	-0.416	-2.78	<.008
Constant	-3.500	0.500	-	-7.00	<.001

Note. $R^2 = .173, F(1, 37) = 7.75, p = .008$. OCD = obsessive-compulsive disorder

Table 4 summarizes a simple linear regression predicting self-compassion from OCD severity (Y-BOCS). The model was significant overall, $F(1, 37) = 7.75, p = .008$, and explained approximately 17.3% of the variance in self-compassion ($R^2 = .173$). A one-point increase in OCD severity was associated with a decrease of 0.416 points in self-compassion ($B = -0.416, SE = 0.149$,

$\beta = -0.416, t = -2.78, p = .008$). These results indicate that higher OCD severity uniquely predicts poorer self-compassion, supporting Hypothesis 1B. Başaran and Gökdağ (2025) revealed that low self-compassion worsens obsessions and compulsions. They emphasize the importance of examining self-related psychological constructs like self-compassion when treating or understanding the maintenance of OCD symptoms. Patients with OCD often experience high levels of "inflated responsibility" and guilt and as symptoms intensify, the capacity for self-kindness diminishes, replaced by self-judgment and isolation.

Table 5

Simple Linear Regression Predicting Psychological flexibility from OCD Severity (N = 39)

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p
OCD	0.514	0.141	0.514	3.65	.001
Constant	2.800	0.500	-	5.60	<.001

Note. $R^2 = .351, F(1, 37) = 13.29, p = .001$; OCD = obsessive-compulsive disorder; psychological flexibility

As shown in Table 5, a simple linear regression was conducted to assess whether OCD severity predicts psychological flexibility, measured using the AAQ-II. The overall model was statistically significant, $F(1, 37) = 13.29, p = .001$, and explained 35.1% of the variance in psychological flexibility ($R^2 = .351$). The parameter estimate for OCD severity was $B = 0.514, SE = 0.141$, and $\beta = .514$, indicating that each one-point increase in OCD severity corresponded to a 0.514-point increase in psychological flexibility a significant effect ($t = 3.65, p = .001$). These results confirm Hypothesis 1C, Silva et al. (2024) suggest that experiential avoidance serves as a core pathological process in OCD, where the rigid attempt to suppress distressing intrusive thoughts actually facilitates the maintenance of the disorder. As OCD symptoms worsen, patients become increasingly trapped in experiential avoidance the urge to suppress or escape uncomfortable thoughts and compulsions. The more one struggles against their obsessions, the more psychologically rigid they become.

Limitations of the Study

Although the sample size of 39 has met the minimum requirement for statistical power, it is still relatively small. Furthermore, the use of purposive sampling in a specific geographic location (Jaipur, Rajasthan) may limit the results from being generalized to the broader population of OCD patients in different cultural or rural contexts. The measures used in the study are self-report inventories. Furthermore, Responses may be influenced by social desirability or the patient's current mood state at the time of testing. This study focused on overall severity rather than specific subtypes which might interact differently with the study variables.

Clinical Implications of the Study

The study has implications in understanding a patient with OCD being the scope of their symptoms merely. It also facilitates the understanding of efficacy of the Acceptance and Commitment Therapy based strategies to break the cycle of rigidity. There is also scope of Integrating Compassion-Focused approaches to combat the intense self-criticism inherent in this population. Implication also lies in assisting patients reclaim time from compulsions to invest in

valued life goals.

Future Directions

Future studies should follow patients over time to see how fluctuations in OCD severity impact psychological flexibility and self-compassion throughout the course of treatment. Given the strong link between OCD and positive psychological variables, research should focus on the efficacy of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy and Compassion-Focused Therapy specifically for the Indian clinical population. Expanding the Construct of Equanimity: Since equanimity did not show a significant relationship here, future research could use qualitative interviews or different scales to explore this variable more in relation to OCD. Additionally, Future research could compare OCD patients with other anxiety disorders or a healthy control group.

Conclusion

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the relationship between OCD severity and four positive psychological constructs: Valued Living, Self-Compassion, Psychological Flexibility, and Equanimity. The results partially supported the hypotheses, revealing that while OCD significantly impacts a patient's ability to remain flexible, compassionate toward themselves, and value-driven, its relationship with equanimity appears more complex and wasn't significantly established in the current study. The findings demonstrate that OCD is not merely a collection of intrusive thoughts and repetitive behaviours, but a condition that deeply affects a person's Self-Compassion, restricts their ability to live according to their Values, and creates Psychological Inflexibility.

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